

**NATURAL LAW THEORY: BIBLICAL-THEOLOGICAL JUSTIFICATION, VALUE, AND
ITS APPLICATIONS IN SOCIETY**

By

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There are legitimate institutions and structures like marriage, family, morals, civil laws, social laws, governments, and political structures that exist in the history of mankind apart from Judeo-Christian civilization and special revelation. As human beings, we share common values, morals, behaviors, rituals, laws, and governing principles with some exceptions and degrees of variation. For example, murder without a lawful excuse is considered a crime in most cultures. How do we explain such magnitude of God's common grace across the cultures and in the entirety of human history? Natural law theory sheds light on the mystery of human morals, structures, and institutions. In this paper, I will first define the natural law, then I will explain the biblical and theological justification, its value, and its applications for society.

First, natural law is defined as the order or rule of human behavior based on human nature as created by God, knowable by all men, through human intuition and reasoning alone, and normative for all human beings. Natural law is independent of any divine revelation.¹ Natural law needs to be distinguished from God's eternal law and human law. God's eternal law is the basis for natural law, just as the purpose of the invention is determined by the mind of the inventor.² On the other hand, human law is constructed by the application of reason of general principles for the common good. Human law relies on natural law; therefore, natural law is the foundation for it.³ Although natural law is imposed on creatures, it is not mechanistic or without

¹ David Haines and Andrew A. Fulford, *Natural Law: A Brief Introduction and Biblical Defense*. (Russia: Davenant Institute, 2017), 5.

² Haines and Fulford, *Natural Law*, 7.

³ Haines and Fulford, 8.

exception. Natural law does not grant autonomy or independence to humans from God's authority and control, rather, it operates under God's control, therefore, we are still dependent on God for our nature, existence, and salvation.⁴

Second, natural law is affirmed by biblical and theological evidence. God has revealed something about his character, morals, and creation to all humans including pagans (Acts 14:17). This general revelation is revealed to all humanity apart from the revelation of scriptures. General revelation includes the testimony of creation to us about the creator (Psalm 19:1-6), rational and moral capacities of image-bearers to distinguish the true God from idols (Romans 1:26-27), facts of our physical and emotional design to understand God's purposes (Romans 1:26-27), a law of conscience written on our hearts (Romans 2:14-15), and a rationale to understand the consequences of sin (Proverbs 1:31).⁵ David Haines and Andrew A. Fulford argue that the first pronouncement of good in Genesis about good created order proclaims the natural law in creation.⁶ In Exodus 18:17-18, Jethro instructed Moses to appoint multiple leaders to lead the congregation of Israel efficiently. Jethro was a non-Israelite who did not have former knowledge of Mosaic law. However, his instruction is of common sense, and it helped Moses when there was no divine instruction.⁷ In Jeremiah 8:7, the prophet contrasts the obedience of creation to its designed order and the disobedience of God's people to his law.⁸ In Romans

⁴ Haines and Fulford, *Natural Law*, 10.

⁵ J. Budziszewski, *Written on the Heart: The Case for Natural Law*, (Downers Grove, Ill: InterVarsity Press, 1997), 180-181.

⁶ Haines and Fulford, *Natural Law*, 51.

⁷ Haines and Fulford, 54.

⁸ Haines and Fulford, 54.

13:1-4, Paul argues that God ordained the political order in the world, and to disobey the government is to disobey God.⁹

Third, the scope and value of general revelation are broad and vague, unlike special revelation. Similar to Mosaic law, natural law supplies the knowledge of God's moral will and sin (Romans 3:20; 7:7). The revelation of knowledge demands obedience and worship. Mosaic law communicates more clearly sin and God's nature which is already revealed by natural law. Interestingly, natural law instigates the sinful nature of human beings (Romans 7:5). Both Mosaic and natural law communicates God's judgment against sin and convicts human sin (Revelation 3:19).¹⁰ Natural law is extremely valuable to argue for the existence of God, condemning sin, and seeking justice for the unborn, and prohibiting same-sex marriages. Since the unbelievers do not submit to the authority of God's word, our point of contact for persuasion is natural law. God penetrated morality in the very being of humans when he created us as his image-bearers.¹¹ In spite of the strong evidence and value, general revelation has its limitations. Humans rebelled against God and obscured general revelation (Romans 3:23). We neglected to see what God has revealed to us and the revelation is suppressed due to the deception of the heart (Jeremiah 17:9).¹²

Fourth, natural law is a great resource and helpful tool because of its potential use for social issues. If natural law is ordained for all human beings, it has normative implications for society. Natural law positions certain moral constraints on the legitimate structures of

⁹ Haines and Fulford, 101.

¹⁰ David VanDrunen, *Natural Law and Evangelical Political Thought*, ed. Bryan T McGraw, Jesse David Covington, and Micah Joel Watson (Lanham, Maryland: Lexington Books, 2013), 88.

¹¹ Budziszewski, *Written on the Heart*, 184-185.

¹² Budziszewski, 182.

institutional life.¹³ Natural law theory is a critical reflective account of human institutions, communities, and their well-being. Natural law theory intends to recognize principles of right action including human rights and human dignity. Humans inherently possess certain rights and governments are bound to protect those rights based on their nature as humans.¹⁴ This argument forms the basis for equality, justice, rights of education and healthcare, rights of protection from murder, slavery, and mistreatment. If humans have inalienable rights by virtue of their humanity, this applies to embryonic and unborn babies, therefore, they should be protected by the norm against the killing of the innocent.¹⁵ These principles could be applied to the institutions of marriage, civil, and judiciary authorities. Paul affirmed natural law truths concerning decency of marriage, the authority of parents over children, and the condemnation of extramarital sexual affairs (1 Corinthians 7). Paul also acknowledges the natural law obligation of society to secure justice through civil authorities.¹⁶

¹³Jean Porter, *Natural and Divine Law: Reclaiming the Tradition for Christian Ethics*. (Ottawa, Ontario: Novalis, 1999), 250.

¹⁴ Robert P. George, *Natural Law and Evangelical Political Thought*, ed. Bryan T McGraw, Jesse David Covington, and Micah Joel Watson (Lanham, Maryland: Lexington Books, 2013), 111.

¹⁵ George, Robert P., *Natural Law and Evangelical Political Thought*, 112-113.

¹⁶ George, Robert P., 100-101.

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